

8T – Fifth-Vectors

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T that is infinite universe in the packet which flatten each other via areas of extremum curvatures, author presents the idea of fifth-vector. That extra term is meant to specify the surface in which the motion occurs. Each surface has a unique fermion distribution which effect the coordinates, author presents a motion that is neither linear nor non-linear and involves linear trajectory across infinite set of surfaces.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2A) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

So now instead of the classification of spin we can represent each coupling term to be a mixture of spins of distinct kind. Define spin operator:

$$\mathcal{L}: [\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{Q}] \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_{[\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{Q}]} \quad (1.64)$$

That is a mapping between the integers and non-integer fields onto a spin operator in such way that the spin is matching the subscript:

$$\mathcal{L}: 0 \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_0$$

$$\mathcal{L}: \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_{1/2}$$

$$\mathcal{L}: 1 \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_1$$

Now each coupling term can be represented in a way that reflect the idea of interacting fields, which are represented by spin operators.

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \rightarrow \mathcal{S}_0 + \mathcal{S}_{1/2} + \mathcal{S}_1 \quad (1.44.A)$$

Let us analyze the idea of four vectors, which are closely related to invariance. Since in our framework we have an even number of universes aspiring infinity in the universe packet (1.2A), the vector must specify which universe out of the packet the motion occurs in, which represents by the parameter s_n .

$$\mathcal{Q}: [x, y, z, t] \rightarrow [x, y, z, t, s_n]$$

$$[(x, y, z, t) \in s_n]$$

So there as to be a clear specification between space and distance. When motion occurs an object coordinate varies in a certain space, the variation depends upon the frame of reference. Since the frame of reference also is effected by the distribution of matter on the universe, it has to be taken into account. So coordinate variation in fourth vectors has to do with relativistic motion, but surface variation is the new idea. This idea imposes a new constraint, that in order to describe the motion we have to specify which universe it occurs. It is also possible to construct the jumps across the manifolds in the packet as a non-linear motion, where you travel in three dimensions, jump to an higher or lower surface and move on those dimensions with a distinct arrow.

$$[(x, y, z, t) \in s_n] \rightarrow [(x, y, z, t) \in s_{n+1}]$$

$$s_n \not\equiv s_{n+1}$$

Since those surfaces have different matter distribution in jumping from surface to surface one must ensure that the trajectory chosen does not have any Fermionic obstacles which manifest themselves in the new surface and had no equivalent in the original surface which the jumped occurred. The idea of variational Fermion distributions was presented by arbitrary variations vanishing into matter, in identical amount but in different configuration, and is considered as one of the two explanations for dark matter:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^{s_1} \in [0,1]$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^K \delta g_i \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^{s_2} \in [0,1]$$

$$\mathcal{R}^{s_1} \not\equiv \mathcal{R}^{s_2}$$

$$K \equiv M$$

Summing up, when we consider motion, the fourth vector must become a fifth vector, which specify surface on which the motion occurs.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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